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Formation and Description of Concepts of Term and Terminology

Mukaddam Alihonova

English Teacher of the Department of English Language Teaching Methods, Namangan State University, Uzbekistan

***Abstract:** The importance of terminology in linguistics cannot be overstated, as it is the core element that allows communication and understanding within the profession. Linguistic terminology is a specialized vocabulary that is used to describe language structures, facts, and processes, hence assisting in the accurate representation and study of many elements of language. Linguists from various linguistic backgrounds and research areas can efficiently exchange ideas, hypotheses, and findings by utilizing agreed-upon words. The importance of terminology in linguistic research and analysis is discussed in this article. It describes how researchers can effectively identify, describe, and compare distinct language traits and phenomena, hence advancing linguistic knowledge and the creation of linguistic theories.*

***Key words:** Linguists, Terminology, hypotheses, Term, Researchers Linguistics, theory, research, role, specialized vocabulary.*

INTRODUCTION

The expansion of our language at the expense of foreign phrases resulted from reforms in our nation intended to stay up with the global community and human contributions to the advancement of science. Consequently, terminology associated with different domains became the main focus of scientific inquiry. Large-scale scientific studies have been conducted thus far on terms and terminology, which is thought of as a collection of terms. Linguists considered terminology issues as early as the 18th and 19th centuries, and it is accurate to assume that the fast industrial development of that period was the origin of this occurrence. Scientific study undertaken at different times has led to varied explanations of concepts of term and terminology. A term is a unique word used in a certain field that aids in the advancement of that field. In social life, phrases frequently have distinct meanings. Thus, any instrument developed for this field's advancement in any field contributes to the development of the field of linguistics. If we define terms differently, we would say that a term is a

word or phrase that is employed in a certain field of knowledge or research to define a particular notion, idea, phenomena, or object.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

There are formal and informal ways to define terms. Various sources define the terms differently. Wikipedia defines a term as "a term (Latin: terminus - "limit") - a word or combination of words that expresses the concept of a special field of knowledge or activity." It is true that professionals in a certain field should be able to grasp and apply them consistently. Terms are considered to be beyond the derivation stage if they exist both as individual words and as word combinations. Although the word "term" originated in Latin, scientists occasionally use the Uzbek word "atama" as an alternative for term. According to experts, the word "atama" ought to be employed in the social and humanities as well as in STEM subjects. Apart from the word "atama", "nomenclature" is also regarded as being synonymous with the term. The distinction between nomenclature and term words is explained by P.P. Nishanov as follows: "A term applied to an object or reality first defines and classifies this object or reality. The terminology does not reflect this. They can only be used for object and thing naming. Consequently, "nomenclature" is a term that is used to name related things and concepts, whereas "term" refers to a broad and distinct notion that is used in a certain subject". This definition makes it clear that the term and word nomenclature cannot be synonyms for one another because of the term's far broader area of use. A team of scientists claim that term refers to a unique function of the word. Among the scientists who identified the term as a "word with a special function" was the Russian linguist G.O.Vinokur. The scientists who agreed with his theories later voiced their opinions. Terms do, in fact, serve as names; yet, they can also be determined by social events and end up being common nouns. In some circumstances, the terminology acquires artistic descriptions after entering social life. The adoption of the term as a separate unit in linguistics resulted in the development of various descriptions and a scientific approach to concerns related to term. According to V. P. Danilenko, the term is in the dictionary and is an explanation offered to lexemes in the same field. Based on such viewpoints, a number of dictionaries of diverse area terminology have been established by research scientists, which might serve as unambiguous evidence of this viewpoint. V. N. Shevchuk defines term as follows: "Term is a word that means "identification" and "expression" in the Middle Ages, and the lexeme "terme" existed in the ancient French language expressed the meaning of a word." The term, in our opinion, represents the name of an object, activity, or action in a field and avoids long explanations throughout the communication process. At the same time, it provides numerous benefits not only to representatives of a particular area, but also to newcomers to that subject. That is why; terminology has become a priority direction of research. A term is a word or a word combination that clearly expresses the concept of something related to science, technology and other fields, the scope of use of which is limited to these fields. For example, linguistic terms: sentence, noun, subject, number, sound...; geometry terms: circle, triangle, etc. The fact that the concept of the term is also expressed in explanatory dictionaries is the foundation for us to create a general understanding. Because, explanations created by summarizing many studies are presented in such dictionaries.

Discussion

A term is a word combination that means a special concept in a certain terminological sphere and at the same time is convenient to use in field communication. In our opinion, semantic accuracy is one of the main characteristics of terms; they have a clear and strictly defined meaning in a certain field of knowledge. For this reason, terms prevent misunderstandings in the process of communication and ensure its clarity and understanding. B. N. Golovin defines the term as follows: "From the point of

view of profession, the term expresses certain professional concepts." In fact, terms are used in a special field of knowledge or profession and may be incomprehensible or unfamiliar to people who are not familiar with this field. The diversity of the definition of the term is characterized by that in many cases the term is an object of several subjects at the same time. Field terminologists define the term from the perspective of their field. For this reason, the concept of terminology is expressed with different definitions in a number of scientific sources. The notion of terminology was first used in 1969, when it was officially recognized at Scientific Conference at Moscow State University. As a result, terminology became a subject. However, some linguists regard it as a scientific path rather than a discipline. The lexical layer of the language is continually being filled with new terms, resulting in a distinct system. Furthermore, the relevant lexical components must be processed and systematized. All of these facts plainly demonstrate the need for a new science - terminology - whose object of study is the term. The earliest work on terminology by the Austrian scientist E. Wuster and the Russian terminologist D. Lotte resulted in the foundation of terminology as a separate science. Terminology is a subfield of linguistics that analyzes terminology and their applications in various professions or disciplines. It is concerned with the classification, and standardization of terminology used to define specific concepts, objects, or events. One of the primary purposes and tasks of terminology is to define and characterize terms. Terminology aims to define and characterize terms through the use of precise and unambiguous definitions. This allows specialists in a specific field to build a shared language and mutual understanding. Wuster, a world-renowned linguist who identified terminology as a separate discipline, laid the groundwork for the creation of innovative techniques in this subject. H. Felber, a representative of the Vienna School of Terminology, for example, attempted to demonstrate that "every term is formed on the basis of a concept." L. Drozd, a Czech scientist, advises researching its structural aspects in order to establish a term. D.S. Lotte, a Russian scientist, presented his advice on "unification of terms and setting the scale of international standards in their use" in the context of terminology. The explanatory dictionary of linguistics defines terminology as follows: Terminology (term + logos-word, instruction) 1. A group of terminology associated with a science, profession, or other subject. 2. The branch of linguistics concerned with the study of the term. Terminology is the systematization and classification of terminology within the above-mentioned subject of study. This makes it easier for field users to locate and retrieve information. H. Dadaboyev considers terminology to be "distinguished by its special place and position in the construction of the modern Uzbek literary language." There are two viewpoints on the role of terminology in the language. According to the first theory, terminology is recognized as an independent layer of the literary language's lexicon, whereas the second theory separates it from the literary language's vocabulary, evaluates it as a "stand-alone" object, and types of speech (dialect, slang, equated to live conversation). When we think of terminology, we think of a complex scientific and technical language, yet it is constructed, expanded, and developed mostly on the basis of ordinary literary language. Terminology's vocabulary, derivation, and grammatical rules are established at the expense of common literary language.

CONCLUSION

Terminology is a field that has grown in relevance in research and the professional world. Using multiple phrases to represent the same notion might make translation more difficult and contribute to confusion and ambiguity. Using terminology helps guarantee that material is consistent and that terms are appropriately translated. Understanding terminology is an essential aspect of being able to perform in a specific field. Terminology is also concerned with the standardization of terms in order to provide consistency and clarity in communication. Organizations or institutions may also adopt terminology standards to promote consistency in the use of terms in a specific subject. Terminology also includes the administration of terminology resources such as terminological dictionaries, terminological

databases, and terminological reference books. It provides specialists and translators with access to credible and authentic information sources. New concepts that develop in a certain subject, in our opinion, require a terminological approach; otherwise, they produce widespread misconceptions and problems.

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